

Rac-9

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-160-3-RAC-30%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	95	Acq. Method Set:	30%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 160 3 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/26/2022 3:51:21 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/20/2022 11:45:54 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	3.920	1096447	50.13	157422
2	4.436	1090647	49.87	136174

Asy-9

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-160-3-ASY-30%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	110	Acq. Method Set:	30%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 3 160 3 asy
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/26/2022 4:05:16 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/20/2022 11:43:51 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	3.935	50667	3.74	7944
2	4.456	1303480	96.26	165077